

Effective Teams Need Effective Frameworks, Vice Versa

How the driver of success in projects are ultimately about people who create value & technologies and adhere to methodologies & schools of thought.

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Executive Summary

Traditional and Modern methodologies for project management and team management has been touted to be very different based on assumptions, principles, practices, processes, and limitations. Further study of literature, research, and field experience portray a more dynamic story of interplay between the applicability and inappropriateness of various methodologies. This depends on the context within which different types of projects operate, strategic drivers that underpin it, economic fuel that constrains or liberates resource provisioning tactics, and people aspects of any social constructs that characterises projects, companies, and institutions more than processes, products, and technologies. The difficult decision points in pursuing profound and impactful human endeavors are rarely those that chooses between what is correct or wrong, nor whether it is truthful or false. What is profoundly difficult is the choice between two correct notions or different workable solutions; conversely, the same can be said between the discernment and choice between the lesser of two evils. What may break the stalemate is simple diligence and the wisdom to go beyond surface noise competing for attention and to understand the signal that beckons to be perceived by which directions and decisions must be made. Ultimately, the wisdom may prove to be a synthesis rather than a contrast of choices; whether that fusion of various lenses and thinking hats is an easy goal or a hard-fought win borne of experience and erudition is a different matter. But, persevere, we must, for so much is at stake. If history is any guide, the consequences of project failures impacts the project teams less but hurt the stakeholders that we frequently ignore more: the taxpayers for their sacrifices and our colleagues who stand to benefit less from projects individually but may helplessly lose livelihoods should those in charge neglect the significance of the responsibility they bear.

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1. Introduction

Much has been said about the evolution of managing the creation of the 'new' within the context of programmes and projects. While as a practice and as a profession, project management emerged more recently, human endeavors which have similar attributes as projects like goals, resources, timetables, social constructs, success factors, failures, and learnings are not new. Humanity and civilisation have built structures and wonders that have required the congregation and collaboration of human thought, energy, and effort (Berkun, 2005; Kerzner, 2009; Meredith & Mantel, 2009). Whether the success factors and deadlines are metaphorical only in some types of projects, historically, other objectives have existential consequences that predicate critical success and survival factors (Nelson, 2007).

The challenge is not much the multifaceted nature of projects at the surface like method of conduct, terms of staffing, stakeholder management, resource utilisation, and timing progress, coordination, and concerns around operations (Cobb, 2012, p.12). Projects are unique "temporary endeavours" in which that temporal essence "fundamentally affects their structure, dynamics, operations and, as a result, their management" (Cobb, 2012, p.4) as opposed to general management.

Ultimately, people, companies, institutions, and nations have goals to seek and the effective deployment of strategy, resources, and time within expectations of quantity and quality are cornerstones of managing endeavours like projects. Such projects are inherently uncertain and ephemeral as opposed to entrenched social stratas, bureaucracies, public administration, and private institutions whose existence is intrinsically unbound by temporary arrangements.

These core values, understandings, assumptions, and principles of environmental context, historical backdrop (Landes, 1999), and contemporary ethos are the true drivers of how people perceive and misconstrue project management, its mechanisms, and its effectiveness. Much of the differences between what we ascribe as traditional versus modern project management are based on these forces rather than the mechanisms employed whether for global cooperation (Stare, 2013), for state level programmes, civil infrastructure, IT projects management, and all other fields that now utilise project management as a tool for driving and sustaining change (Quist, 2015). What does not change is change itself and that people will always be a part of this construct called projects (Lindstrom & Jeffries, 2004).

2. Main

2.1. Traditional, In Theory

Traditional project management, as a field and profession, has its roots at the turn of the twentieth century. Project management, as a practice though, which in essence marshals resources in the attainment of objectives within specified timeframes driven by needs or wants of society or individuals is nothing new (Berkun, 2005).

Among the key techniques and practices that defines traditional methods are represented by Programme Evaluation Review Technique (PERT), Critical Path Method (CPM), Critical Chain Project Management (CCPM), and Six Sigma among others. The nature of traditional methods prescribe formal specifications with assumptions of minimal deviations from project inception where each succeeding steps become officially accepted in bulk prior to moving through the process (Palmquist et al., 2013).

These come in many flavors like the often mentioned waterfall methods in software engineering that follow a process outlined below (Table 2.1.1.).

Waterfall Methods
<i>Feasibility of system / Validation</i>
<i>Requirements gathering and software planning / Validation</i>
<i>Design of product / Verification</i>
<i>Detailed design / Verification</i>
<i>Coding and Unit testing</i>
<i>Components & Modules Integration and Product Verification</i>
<i>Implementation with System testing</i>
<i>Operation and Maintenance with Revalidation</i>

Table 2.1.1. - Traditional Waterfall Method For Software Construction (Boehm, 2000).

Traditional Project Management Phases	
Project Phases	Steps
Initiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Project selection aligned with resource limits</i> • <i>Benefits recognition</i> • <i>Sanction documentation preparations</i> • <i>Project manager assignment</i>
Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Work / Requirements definition</i> • <i>Work quantity and quality</i> • <i>Resource definitions</i> • <i>Activities scheduling</i> • <i>Risk evaluation</i>
Execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Project team members negotiations</i> • <i>Work directions and management</i> • <i>Ongoing team improvements</i>
Monitoring and control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Progress tracking</i> • <i>Target vs Actual Outcome comparison</i> • <i>Variances and impacts analysis</i> • <i>Adjustments</i>
Closure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Accomplished work verification</i> • <i>Contract closure</i> • <i>Financial closure</i> • <i>Administrative closure</i>

Table 2.1.2. - Traditional Project Management Phases
(Project Management Institute, 2008; Kerzner, 2009).

The crucial assumption and philosophy is certainty in lock step within each key process node while going through the process. This is rooted as an answer to industrialisation and factory models that led to the development and formalisation of scientific management as formally prescribed by Frederick Taylor but whose economic principles traces back to Adam Smith (Grönroos, 1994).

2.2. Traditional, In Practice

One perceives a pattern emerge when observing and studying both the successes and failures of traditional methodologies in different contexts and project types: (a) a rigid structure executing within siloed organisations or bureaucracies, (b) that failures are norms than exceptions, and (c) that traditional methods also abide by so called agile principles in encouraging optimal execution and team productivity (Nelson, 2007). This should hardly be the analysis. As an example, many cases of IT systems implementation failures (Nelson, 2007) are characterised by shortcomings not in method but in people and processes.

People-related Risks
<i>Support from top & middle management is lacking</i>
<i>Project manager is weak or technically unqualified</i>
<i>Stakeholder involvement and participation is lacking or missing</i>
<i>Commitment of teams in projects are lacking</i>
<i>Important knowledge and skills in team member are lacking</i>
<i>Overextended and overschedule domain & subject matter experts</i>

Table 2.2.1. - People-related Risks (Kappelman, McKeeman, & Zhang, 2006).

Process-related Risks
<i>Documented requirement and success criteria lacking</i>
<i>Change control process under- or mis-managed</i>
<i>Schedule planning and management is ineffective</i>
<i>Breakdown of communications among stakeholders</i>
<i>Resources re-assignments to a higher priority work</i>
<i>Business case is non-existent</i>

Table 2.2.2. - Process-related Risks (Kappelman, McKeeman, & Zhang, 2006).

Often overlooked, too frustratingly if the author may add, is a simple assumption that keeps being ignored: stable specifications (Meredith & Mantel, 2009). Traditional methods assumes a high level of certainty in specifications to enable the accurate modelling and computation of project execution and operational parameters. The applicability of traditional and formal methods is higher than agile methods in projects for civil infrastructures, factory tooling and construction implementations, data gathering projects for public governance, and others (Kannan, Jhajharia, & Verma, 2014).

Not to be ignored, schedules and acts of scheduling primarily serve three purposes (Berkun, 2005): (a) “commitments about when things will be done”, (b) “encourage everyone who's contributing to a project to see her efforts as part of a whole, and invest in making her pieces work with others, and (c) “give the team a tool to track progress and to break work into manageable chunks.” Project management is not easy in practice, but with the use of a good system that keeps customers and stakeholders informed while keeping things pleasant, some delays can be managed positively (Knight, Thomas, & Angus, 2013).

2.3. Modern, In Theory

It would be hard to ascertain exact dates or inflection points when modern project management began and traditional project management ended (Kannan, Jhajharia & Verma, 2014). It is probably an arduous task to define cleanly, clearly, and with minimal reason for arguments what ‘traditional’ is and what ‘modern’ is in the first place.

For the sake of discussion, simplicity, and practicality, we will use the emergence of iterative and incremental forms of implementation where project are broken down into consistent timeboxes (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016). They are “more like a timed race than a 10-kilometer race: run as far as possible in 60 minutes” (Cohn, 2006, p.27). These technique allow shorter time horizon to unravel uncertainties, gather team feedback to improve performance, and adapt directions based on customer and user interactions.

Apart from these, principles and values underpin the techniques and mechanics of most of these methods, thus allowing for people (Lalsing, Kishnah, & Pudaruth, 2012) to take more part in the effectiveness and execution of modern project management.

While modern methods are commonly attributed to Agile methods, these are but “a subset of iterative and evolutionary methods” (Larman, 2009, p.9) which “embrace change, but not chaos” (Larman, 2009, p.14). While Agile has been interpreted to be at farther ends of the

spectrum of chaos or rigidity, Agile methods espouses regular anchors of stability through disciplined measurements in iterative time boxes for adaptive planning, promotion of evolutionary delivery, and preparations for rapid and flexible response to change. Larman (2009), reiterates repeatedly that *If agile methods have a motto, it is embrace change. If agile methods have a strategic point, it is manoeuvrability.*

From a paradigm perspective, this is now famously attributed to the family of agile methodologies like eXtreme Programming (XP), Scrum, Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM), Scaled Agile Framework (SAFE), Lean, and others. While commonly used in IT related projects, the principles, assumptions, methods, and practices within so called agile methods first took hold in other domains with some variations to the theme. Some of the examples of these are Spiral Model of software engineering (Bajwa, Singh, & Sharma, 2012), statistical models of total quality management applied to organisation transformation as part of cycles of improvement in organisations beginning in the 1920s (American Society for Quality, 2017; Neave, 1987), Kaizen/Plan-Do-Check-Act cycles (Bulsuk, 2009), and other methodologies with similar philosophies.

Scrum framework, like XP before it, has emerged as among the most used among these agile methodologies in companies and startups using key principles and practices to guide the execution of the Scrum process (Palmquist et al., 2013). The adoption, in the experience of this author, may stem from the simplicity and malleability of the framework as well as the vibrant activity in both online communities and events in the recent decade.

Principles & Values	Practices & Techniques
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Common Language</i> • <i>Common Definition of Done or DOD</i>
Inspection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Frequent inspection of artefacts, but not too much</i> • <i>Performed by skilled inspector at point of work</i>
Adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adjustments made as soon as possible to remove variances</i>

Table 2.3.1. - Scrum Principles & Values (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016).

Role	Responsibilities
The Product Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Responsible for maximizing the value of the product and the work of the Development Team</i>
The Development Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Professionals who do the work of delivering a potentially releasable Increment of “Done” product at the end of each Sprint</i>
The Scrum Master	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Responsible for ensuring Scrum is understood and enacted</i>

Table 2.3.2. - Key Scrum Team Roles (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016).

Event	Description
The Sprint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A time-box between 1-4 weeks during which a “Done”, useable, and potentially releasable product Increment is developed</i>
Sprint Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regular planning at the start of every iteration</i> • <i>This may typically be split into two parts, one focuses on scope and the other focuses on the team</i>
Daily Scrum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A short (e.g. 15 minutes) time-boxed daily event for the Development Team to synchronize activities and create a plan for the current day</i>
Sprint Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Review at the end of sprint to inspect the increment and to adjust the Product Backlog when necessary</i> • <i>The team and stakeholders discuss about what was done</i>
Sprint Retrospective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The opportunity for the Scrum Team to inspect itself and identify areas for improvements</i>

Table 2.3.3. - Key Scrum Events (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016).

Artifact	Description
Product Backlog	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A summary and list of product scope and requirements</i> • <i>May typically and practically be grouped as new, enhancements, or defects</i>

Sprint Backlog	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Backlog items from the Product backlog prioritized for the current sprint • Specified with a certain level of details to help achieve the sprint goals
Increment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sum of Completed and “Done” sprint backlog items

Table 2.3.4. - Scrum Artifacts (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016).

Another commonly practiced method is Atern, based on DSDM, as illustrated below (Figure 2.3.1.).

Figure 2.3.1. - Atern, a commonly used process framework, Lifecycle Diagram (Agile Business Consortium, 2008)

Atern (DSDM) Lifecycle Phases	
Phases	Remarks
Pre-project	<i>Start up and preparations</i>
Feasibility	<i>Examine the Project Viability</i>
Foundations	<i>Determine the Business Requirements</i>
Exploration	<i>Develop Models & Prototypes</i>
Engineering	<i>Develop a Robust Solution</i>
Deployment	<i>Implement the Product Release</i>

Post-Project	<i>Assess the Benefits</i>
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Table 2.3.5. - Atern Lifecycle Phases (Carroll & Morris, 2015)

2.4. Modern, In Practice

Many projects implemented in governments, institutions, enterprises, startups, and other sectors that used agile still fails (Shore & Warden, 2008; Nelson, 2008; Kappelman, McKeeman, & Zhang, 2006; Tanner & Willingham, 2014). On the other hand, there are several quantitative and qualitative evidence that shows successes in adopting agile practices both in co-located teams (Layman, et al., 2006) and globally distributed and virtual teams (Painter, et al., 2016; Layman, et al., 2006; Bilczynska, 2014; Berg & Holtbrügge, 2010).

Poppendieck & Poppendieck (2003) and Fojtik (2010) proposes reduction in waste in an iterative way: “the first step to implementing lean development is learning to see waste. The second step is to uncover the biggest sources of waste and eliminate them. The next step is to do it again.” They also highlighted misconceptions and assumptions about teams and projects that plague across frameworks saying “Development is quite different than production. Think of development as creating a recipe and production as following the recipe” (Poppendieck & Poppendieck, 2003, p.15).

In retrospect, most agile successes stem from officially transforming existing traditional project management into something that espouses agile principles and methods. This consequently changes the expectations and assumptions of key stakeholders, project management team, and implementation team (Carroll & Morris, 2015). A cornerstone assumption of Agile methods is the mindset change and prioritisation of value creation and delivery where backlog scope estimations are variable while resources and time are fixed within timeboxes and/or roadmap. Contrary to misconceptions “agile teams do a lot of planning but is spread out much more evenly over the entire project” and that “agile teams squarely face the critical factor that many non-agile teams ignore - uncertainty” (Cohn, 2006).

Mode	Traditional Plan Driven	Agile Value Driven
Fixed	<i>Requirements</i>	<i>Resources & Time</i>
Estimate	<i>Resources & Time</i>	<i>Features</i>

Table 2.4.1. - Paradigm Shift In Project Execution Priorities

If the assumptions and expectations did not change, value creation and appreciation will not be perceived which paradoxically can flag projects as failure even when benefits are realised (Shore & Warden, 2008). Conversely, the same can be said of traditional project assumptions and successes based on time, resources, quality, and deliverables but whose benefits and adoption are not achieved (Turk, France, & Rumpe, 2005).

Both in literature (Shore & Warden, 2008) and in professional experience, it is the author's opinion that one should not use or misuse agile in the pursuit of faster delivery, higher productivity, or other proposed outcomes of agile methods. It is indeed, not a silver bullet for bad management techniques. Shore & Warden (2008) wisely remarked that agile's "benefits ... come from working differently, not from working faster." This author further posits that a key consequence of agile, if done right with the right reasons and the right support, is increased team cohesion and professional well-being which indirectly impacts productivity as a natural consequence than an awkwardly forced control mechanism and choice in projects to push team efforts.

2.5. Traditional and Modern Fusion

There are clear benefits in executing projects that merges Traditional and Modern methodologies in a hybrid fashion (Quist, 2015). In fact, based on empirical data and experience, Agile 'methods' are rarely followed religiously as per prescribed due to many reasons like misunderstanding the concepts or having conflicting interpretations within an organisations of what makes Agile methods "Agile" versus the fundamental "agile" mindset and behaviour that is equally, if not more important than strict and rigid obedience to any single method.

Many of the values of the Agile Manifesto (Manifesto for Agile Software Development, 2001) that espouses promotion of technical excellence, good communications, customer satisfaction, and realising benefits early on are not in contrast with traditional methods. In fact, these are core to traditional method assumptions and principles also (Stare, 2013).

In practice, when a practitioner plots the lifecycle of most projects that adheres to modern methods into a traditional diagram or report format or plan like network diagrams or gantt charts, a curious pattern emerges. In the author's personal experience and practice, we call it the 5-Ps of fractal method alignment in which a geometric similarity exists in how policies, programmes, projects, processes, and people operations look like.

Figure 2.5.1. Waterfall (blue) and Iterative/Agile methods (color-coded team, grouped by module/feature/concern)

Said in another way, the best of modern methods which is still inspired by traditional ones looks the same but is simply executed at a time scale and frequency that is more dynamic.

Parallel execution becomes more easily visible from a plan illustration perspective as well (i.e. clustered and pod-like mapping throughout in a timetable chart visual) as above (Figure 2.5.1.) where each group operate in micro-iterations and daily rituals done (Figure 2.5.2.), not for rituals' sake but for cohesion and encouragement of positive group norms (Duhigg, 2016). Guidance on daily rhythm and prioritisation are simple and supported by fundamental questions on purpose and goals (Figure 2.5.3.). These strategies and team operational cycles are typically visualised whenever possible to facilitate faster understanding, often at a glance, which is quite useful especially in hectic and attention starved times (Bryson, Ackerman, Eden, 2014).

Figure 2.5.2. - Micro-iterations and daily ritual cycles.

Figure 2.5.3. - Team prioritisation thought processes.

The Agile Manifesto, as outlined below, provides guidance over key aspects of thinking (Manifesto for Agile Software Development, 2001). It is of utmost importance to note, for example, that words used are important and interpretations sometimes stem from oversimplification as a function of lack of diligence over simplification which is an important exercise to control unnecessary complexity.

Agile Manifesto		
<p><i>We are uncovering better ways of developing software by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work we have come to value:</i></p>		
<i>Individuals and interactions</i>	<i>over</i>	<i>Processes and tools</i>
<i>Working software</i>	<i>over</i>	<i>Comprehensive documentation</i>
<i>Customer collaboration</i>	<i>over</i>	<i>Contract negotiation</i>

<i>Responding to change</i>	<i>over</i>	<i>Following a plan</i>
<i>That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left more.</i>		

Table 2.5.1. - Agile Manifesto (Manifesto for Agile Software Development, 2001).

The manifesto, perhaps unintentionally, highlights, in bold text the second statement group (i.e. “**Individuals and interactions over processes and tools**”) while reducing the size of the third statement group (i.e. ‘*That is ...*’). This author was one of the earliest supporter and signatories of the manifesto and was mentored directly by some of the founders and was directly taught by leaders of key alliances like the Scrum Alliance. Personally and in discussions with mentors, there is agreement that there has been major misinterpretations and misconception (e.g. ‘agile has no planning’, ‘agile is inapt for long-range roadmap’, or ‘agile is not good because there is no documentation’) that could have been avoided if readers read quite clearly what the manifesto says.

Work Themes Effectiveness	
Themes and Characteristics	Effectiveness Criteria
Job Design <i>Management of Self</i> <i>Encouragement of Participation</i> <i>Variety of Tasks</i> <i>Significance of Tasks</i> <i>Identity of Tasks</i>	Productivity Satisfaction Judgements
Interdependence <i>Relationships of Tasks</i> <i>Relationships of Goals</i> <i>Feedback and Rewards</i>	
Composition <i>Diversity of Team Members</i> <i>Levels of Flexibility</i> <i>Optimal Team Size</i> <i>Team Work Preferences and Dynamics</i>	
Context <i>Training</i> <i>Support from Management</i> <i>Communication/Cooperation Levels</i>	
Process	

<i>Potency of Procedures</i> <i>Support of Social Constructs</i> <i>Sharing of Workloads</i> <i>Communication/Cooperation Levels</i>	
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Table 2.5.2. - Work Theme Effectiveness Themes and Characteristics (Campion, Papper, Medsker, 1996)

Environment Design, as equally used in plot formation in literature, is often an underrepresented factor in frameworks and methodologies (Campion, Papper, & Medsker, 1996). Some go to certain lengths in defining it in more detail than others, like eXtreme Programming’s ergonomics for hexagon shaped tables where groups of 3 pairs of programmers/designers work together (Lindstrom & Jeffries, 2004). There are variations to this but it is clear that creating the physical environment is a crucial foundation for encouraging focus, productivity, and collaboration, all in good measure and balance. As Campbell & Moyers (1991) remarked, “The achievement of the hero is one that he is ready for and it’s really a manifestation of his character. It’s amusing the way in which the landscape and conditions of the environment match the readiness of the hero.”

Like fiction and plot development from another profession, the key actors in projects and teams are rarely just about the antagonist and protagonist. The environment, nature, context, and its portrayal are crucial elements of the flow and constrain the actors far consistently than singular actions.

Apart from this, diversity (see Annex C, Table C.1.) --- in several dimensions, like roles, personalities, strengths, effective group norms, dynamics, structure, and leadership styles at all levels --- in teams is crucial when supported by relevant philosophies, the right group norms (Rozovsky, 2015), and environments that encourage trust (McKnight, Cummings, & Chervany, 1998; Jarvenpaa, Shaw, & Staples, 2004). Historically, diversity has always been wise, as can be seen from highly democratic but contextually flexible pirate crews (Minster, 2017; The Pirate Crew, 2003; Who Is Who - Pirate Ranks on Ship, 2017) (see Annex C, Table C.2.) or highly specialised surgical teams (Brooks, 1995) (see Annex C, Table C.3.).

3. Moving Forward

In many ways, the future and the path ahead for most teams already have archetypes in the present. Numerous successful companies, through grounded academic and industry research, have shown that the discourse around what differentiates methodologies, the critiques of their effectiveness through time and space, and the conflicting results that arise in

misunderstanding and misusing certain frameworks for the wrong ends may be missing the point. What may be needed is a different perspective and a unifying thought process which is guided by adopting what is best from different philosophies.

Figure 3.1. - The Five Keys To A Successful Team in Google [and maybe, your team too] (Rozovsky, 2015).

Progress in project management and effective team management should also be viewed in a more transcendental aspect wherein purpose, self-realisation, and impact is central to the strategic, implementation, and operational aspects of project and people endeavors. As Google Project Aristotle concluded (Duhigg, 2016), what makes teams tick may be age old wisdom which most good managers and leaders already know: teams work well in trust and in knowing that they are listened to and that they matter.

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C. Annex

Belbin's Nine Team Roles		
Name	Characteristics and Role	Allowable weaknesses
Plant	<i>Typically highly creative and good at solving problems unconventionally. Imaginative, free-thinking, generates lots of ideas, and solves difficult challenges.</i>	<i>May ignore details sometimes due to being too pre-occupied to communicate more. Often absent-minded or forgetful.</i>
Resource Investigator	<i>Inquisitive in nature to find ideas to incorporate back to the team. Outgoing, extroverted, enthusiastic. Explores opportunities and develops contacts.</i>	<i>May become too over-optimistic and lose interest once initial enthusiasm has passed. Might be forgetful in following up on a lead.</i>
Coordinator	<i>Needed in a team to focus on the team objectives and delegate work appropriately. Confident, matures, identifies talent, and clarifies goals.</i>	<i>Might be seen as manipulative and might offload their share of workload. May over-delegate and leaving themselves with less work to do.</i>
Shaper	<i>Ensures the team keeps moving and does not lose focus or momentum while providing the necessary drive. Very dynamic and thrives under pressure and has the courage to overcome obstacles.</i>	<i>May be prone to provocation and sometimes offend people. They may risk becoming too aggressive and ill-humoured in their attempts to get work done.</i>
Monitor evaluator	<i>The logical thinking role that makes impartial judgements where needed and weighs team options in an objective way.</i>	<i>May lack the drive and ability to inspire and can be overly critical. Can be slow in decision making.</i>
Teamworker	<i>By being versatile in identifying the work needed to be done, helps the team to gel and impart cooperation and diplomacy. Listens to others and reduces friction.</i>	<i>Can be indecisive during difficult situations and tends to avoid confrontation.</i>
Implementer	<i>Practical, reliable, and efficient in turning ideas into workable strategies and actions to carry it out as effectively and as efficiently.</i>	<i>Can be somewhat inflexible and slow to respond to possibilities and to relinquish personal plans in favour of other positive changes.</i>
Completer Finisher	<i>Very effective when used to polish and scrutinise works for errors, subjecting it to the highest standards. Painstaking and conscientious, seeks, polishes, and perfects errors.</i>	<i>May unduly worry too much and delegate reluctantly and others could accuse them of taking their perfectionism to the extreme.</i>

Specialist	<i>Bears the necessary in-depth knowledge of a key area to the team. Self-starter and dedicated, they provide specialist knowledge and skills.</i>	<i>May tend to contribute on narrow fronts only and can dwell on technicalities. May overload you with information.</i>
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Table C.1. - The nine team roles (Maylor, 2010, p.256, citing Belbin, 1993).

Typical Caribbean Pirate Crew	
Name	Function
Captain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Commands the ship and its crews.</i> • <i>Has full uncontested authority during battle.</i>
First Mate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pirate ships usually did not have First Mates; it is the Quartermasters who perform their duties.</i> • <i>First Mate takes command of the ship if the Captain is unable to perform his duties.</i>
Quartermaster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Quartermaster is the second in command and the Captain's right hand; takes charge of the ship when the Captain is not around.</i> • <i>Can punish men if they are not performing their duties or disobeys commands.</i>
Sailing Master	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Steers the ship, takes charge of piloting and navigation.</i>
Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Helmsman, the one who steers the ship.</i>
Gunner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Crew who is in-charge of the artillery and guns.</i>
Powder Monkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Young boys who are part of the gun crews and assists in operating artillery.</i> • <i>They are paid little, poorly treated and are often expendable.</i>
Boatswain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reports to the Quartermaster or the Captain.</i> • <i>Skilled seamen who has duties ranging from anchoring to naval provisions.</i>
Surgeons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Treats diseases and wounds of crew members.</i>
Cooks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Prepares the food for the crew.</i>
Carpenter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Handles the ship repairs such as filling holes and keeps the ship afloat.</i>

Table C.2. - Typical Caribbean Pirate Crew
(Minster, 2017; The Pirate Crew, 2003; Who Is Who - Pirate Ranks on Ship, 2017).

Typical Surgical Teams, as metaphor for development teams	
Role	Function
Surgeon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Chief and leads the team.</i>
Co-pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Less experienced than a surgeon but able to do the surgeon's tasks.</i>
Administrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>In-charge of money, people, machines, space, etc.</i>
Editor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Cleans up and supports surgeon's work.</i>
Program clerk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Handles and keeps the technical records.</i>
Toolsmith	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>In-charge of taking care and handling surgeon's tools and utilities.</i>
Tester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Debugs and creates component tests for the system.</i>

Table C.3. - Typical Surgical Teams (Brooks, 1995).